

Bank Victoria Sharia and Conventional: Mapping Research Topics using Library Research

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Abstract

This research aims to map research topics surrounding Bank Victoria Sharia and Conventional with a qualitative approach, which is in the nature of a library research. The data collection technique is: first, open the Perish/Harzing software, then search for journals based on the title words category with the key word " Bank Victoria Sharia and Conventional " within the entire year period. Second, collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles. Third, download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) format from all journals for which data has been collected. Fourth, enter the RIS data file into Mendeley software Desktop. Data analysis technique by mapping research topics around Bank Victoria Sharia and Conventional based on the journals that have been collected. The research results show that There are 2 Mapping Research Topics using literature studies regarding Bank Victoria Sharia and Conventional. The implication and contribution of this research is the mapping of research topics surrounding Bank Victoria Sharia and Conventional, both those that are often or rarely researched by researchers, so that other researchers can find out the gaps in research on this topic.

Keywords: Bank Victoria Sharia and Conventional; Library Research

Introduction

Bank Victoria Syariah is a sharia bank operating in Indonesia. Currently, PT Victoria Investama Tbk. (VICO) has taken over the shares of PT Bank Victoria Syariah by pouring in funds amounting to IDR 288 billion. Apart from that, there is additional capital to be placed in Bank Victoria Syariah as well as a search for domestic and foreign investors to acquire the bank. Although there is no specific information regarding the current development of Bank Victoria Syariah, it can be concluded that this bank is undergoing a change in ownership and additional capital to strengthen its position in the market.

Based on the results of previous research, there are several studies that discuss the financial performance of Bank Victoria Syariah after the spin-off. The following are some of the findings from this research: The first research shows that there are differences in the financial performance of Bank Victoria Syariah before and after the spin-off. However, these two studies do not provide specific information regarding the comparison of financial performance. The second research shows that Bank Victoria Syariah had a lower liquidity ratio compared to Bank Syariah Bukopin in the same period. Bank Victoria Syariah has undergone a change in ownership and additional capital to strengthen its position in the market. This shows that Bank Victoria Syariah is trying to improve its financial performance. The third research shows that Bank Victoria Syariah is not yet efficient in managing its financing and income optimally. This could have an impact on Bank Victoria Syariah's income. From these findings, it can be concluded that Bank Victoria Syariah's financial performance after the

spin-off still needs to be improved. Bank Victoria Syariah needs to make efforts to increase liquidity ratios and efficiency in managing its financing and income. Apart from that, increasing capital and seeking domestic and foreign investors could be a solution to strengthen Bank Victoria Syariah's position in the market.

The aim of this research is to map research topics surrounding Bank Victoria Sharia and Conventional uses library research (library research). The difference between this research and previous research is that this research explains all research topics regarding Bank Victoria Sharia and Conventional, so that it can be a reference for other researchers. The implication and contribution of this research is the mapping of research topics surrounding Bank Victoria Sharia and Conventional, both those that are often or rarely researched by researchers, so that other researchers can find out the gaps in research on this topic.

Literature Review

Bank Victoria is part of the Victoria Group group, which has been established since 1992. This bank was then transformed into a sharia bank with the name Bank Victoria Syariah in 2009. Bank Victoria Syariah offers various financial products and services based on sharia principles, including savings, financing, sharia deposits, and other services in accordance with Islamic law. Bank Victoria Syariah has a number of branches and services in various regions in Indonesia. They can also provide electronic banking services, such as internet banking, mobile banking, and ATM, for customer convenience. Bank Victoria Syariah is committed to operating in accordance with sharia principles which prohibit usury (interest), maysir (gambling), and gharar (uncertainty). They comply with sharia regulations and carry out their business processes based on Islamic ethics.

Library research is a type of research that focuses on the analysis, understanding and synthesis of existing literature in a particular field of knowledge or topic. The aim of Library Research research is to identify the latest developments, weaknesses, strengths, findings and trends in the relevant research field. In contrast to experimental research or field research, Library Research research does not involve collecting primary data through observation, interviews, or experiments. Instead, researchers collect data from secondary sources such as books, scientific journals, articles and other academic documents. After collecting data, researchers then analyze, compare, and organize the literature to achieve a deeper understanding of the topic under study.

Methodology

This research uses a qualitative approach in the nature of a library research. The research object is Bank Victoria Sharia and Conventional. The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is research journal articles about Bank Victoria Sharia and Conventional. The source of data collection came from searching the accredited national journal Sinta via the Garuda website (Garba Rujukan Digital) and Perish/Harzing software. Data analysis tools use Microsoft Excel and Mendeley Desktop software.

Data collection techniques include: (1) opening the Perish/Harzing software, then searching for journals based on the title words category with the key word " Bank Victoria Sharia and Conventional " within the entire year period; (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF

(Portable Document Format) formats from all journals for which data has been collected; and (4) enter the RIS data file into Mendeley software Desktop. Data analysis technique by mapping research topics around Bank Victoria Shariah and Conventional based on the journals that have been collected.

Results and Discussion

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Bank Victoria Syariah

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 22 topics related to the financial performance of Bank Victoria Syariah, namely:

First, the bank guarantee uses deposit collateral. Bank guarantees use deposit guarantees, which means the customer submits deposits as collateral to the bank to obtain a bank guarantee. Deposits are used as bank guarantees by customers for practical and efficient reasons so as to meet the demands of running a business smoothly in a short time. In the bank guarantee agreement, it is best to draw up a deed of agreement that confirms the position of the bank guarantee if the debtor defaults. One of the banks that provides deposit guarantees in bank guarantee agreements is PT. Bank Victoria Syariah Jakarta.

Second, the influence of Non-Performing Financing/NPF, Capital Adequacy Ratio/CAR, Financing to Deposit Ratio/FDR, Operational Costs on Operating Income/BOPO, inflation, Mudharabah financing, Musyarakah financing, and Murabahah financing on profitability. A high NPF can affect a bank's profitability because the bank must prepare loss reserves to cover problem loans. A study shows that NPF has a positive and significant influence on Mudharabah and Musyarakah financing. A high CAR indicates that the bank has sufficient capital to cover the risks faced. A study shows that CAR has a positive and significant influence on returns for Mudharabah deposits. A high FDR indicates that the bank provides more financing than receiving third party funds. A study shows that FDR has a negative and significant influence on returns for Mudharabah deposits. A high BOPO indicates that the bank's operational costs are greater than the bank's operating income. A study shows that BOPO has a negative and significant influence on bank profitability. A study shows that inflation has a negative and significant influence on bank profitability. A study shows that Mudharabah financing has a positive and significant influence on bank profitability. A study shows that Musyarakah financing has a positive and significant influence on Mudharabah financing. A study shows that Murabahah financing has a positive and significant influence on bank profitability.

Third, the influence of Third Party Funds on financing. Simultaneously, TPF has a positive and significant effect on murabahah financing. Partially, DPK has a positive and significant effect on mudharabah financing.

Fourth, the influence of company age on financial performance. Based on the search results, there are several studies that discuss the influence of company age on financial performance. The following are the findings from several of these studies: Research on industrial sub-sector manufacturing companies shows that company age has a negative but significant effect on financial performance. Research on manufacturing companies listed on the IDX shows that company age does not have a significant effect on financial performance. Research at Bank Victoria Syariah shows that company age does not have a significant effect on financial performance. From these findings, there are differences in research results regarding the effect of company age on

financial performance. However, in general, it can be concluded that the effect of company age on financial performance is not always significant. Therefore, other factors such as company size, institutional ownership and managerial ownership also need to be considered in measuring a company's financial performance.

Fifth, the influence of Mudharabah and Musyarakah financing on profits. Based on the search results, there are several studies that discuss the effect of Mudharabah and Musyarakah financing on profits. The following are the findings from several of these studies: Research at PT. Bank Syariah Bukopin shows that simultaneously Mudharabah and Musyarakah financing have a positive and significant effect on net profit. Research at Bank Muamalat Indonesia shows that Mudharabah financing has the most dominant influence on profit levels. Apart from that, other research at Bank Muamalat Indonesia also shows that Mudharabah and Musyarakah financing have a positive and significant effect on net profit. Research at Bank BRI Syariah shows that Mudharabah and Musyarakah financing have a positive and significant effect on net profit. From these findings, it can be concluded that Mudharabah and Musyarakah financing have a positive and significant influence on profits at Islamic banks. Therefore, banks need to pay attention to these factors in managing their business in order to increase profits and achieve optimal profitability.

Sixth, the influence of Murabahah receivables, Mudharabah financing and Musyarakah financing on Return On Assets/ROA. Based on the search results, there are several studies that discuss the influence of Murabahah receivables, Mudharabah financing, and Musyarakah financing on Return On Assets (ROA). The following are the findings from several of these studies: Research at Bank Syariah Mandiri shows that Mudharabah and Musyarakah financing have a positive and significant influence on ROA. Research at Bank BNI Syariah shows that Murabahah receivables, Mudharabah financing and Musyarakah financing have a positive and significant influence on ROA. Research at PT. Bank Negara Indonesia Syariah shows that Mudharabah, Murabahah and Musyarakah financing has a positive and significant influence on ROA. From these findings, it can be concluded that Murabahah receivables, Mudharabah financing, and Musyarakah financing have a positive and significant influence on ROA in Islamic banks. Therefore, banks need to pay attention to these factors in managing their business in order to increase ROA and achieve optimal profitability.

Seventh, comparison of financial performance with Bank Syariah Bukopin.

Eighth, the influence of company size, inflation, Capital Adequacy Ratio/CAR, Financing to Deposit Ratio/FDR on Non-Performing Financing/NPF.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Conventional Victoria Banks

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 999 topics related to the performance of Bank Victoria Sharia and Conventional employees, namely:

First, the influence of training and motivation on employee performance. From the findings of several studies, it can be concluded that training and work motivation have a positive and significant influence on employee performance.

Therefore, companies need to pay attention to these factors in managing employees in order to improve performance and achieve company goals.

Second, the influence of Non Performing Loans/NPL, Net Interest Margin/NIM, Operational Costs on Operating Income/BOPO, and Capital Adequacy Ratio/CAR on Return On Assets/ROA.

Third, measuring the level of company health using the RGEC method. The RGEC (Risk Profile, Good Corporate Governance, Earning, and Capital) method is used to measure the health level of banking companies, including Bank Victoria. The following are the steps for measuring the level of company health using the RGEC method at Bank Victoria: Risk Profile: See how well the bank manages existing company risks. Several indicators used in this measurement include NPL (Non-Performing Loan), LDR (Loan to Deposit Ratio), CAR (Capital Adequacy Ratio), and ROA (Return on Assets). Good Corporate Governance: Seeing how well the bank carries out good and correct corporate governance. Several indicators used in this measurement include the level of compliance with rules and regulations, organizational structure, and management quality. Earning: See how much income the bank generates. Several indicators used in this measurement include ROA, ROE (Return on Equity), and NIM (Net Interest Margin). Capital: See how much capital the bank has. Several indicators used in this measurement include CAR and leverage ratio. From the results of the analysis, the health level of Bank Victoria can be known and can be used as a reference for making the right business decisions. Therefore, the RGEC method can help companies measure financial performance and overall company health.

Fourth, the influence of service quality, trust and promotion on customer loyalty.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded that there are 2 Mapping Research Topics using literature studies regarding Bank Victoria Sharia and Conventional.

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